

REMOTE SENSING OF THE ATMOSPHERE AND STUDY OF NEUTRAL POINTS OF ATMOSPHERIC POLARIZATION

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Abstract. Polarization is one of the four basic physical properties of solar radiation. After the solar radiation reaches the surface of these media, it reflects, scatters or refracts, and exhibits different degrees of polarization. We use Rayleigh scattering model to get the simulation results of the sky polarization field. We use polarized fisheye camera to collect the sky polarization image, and calculate the distribution pattern of DOLP (degree of linear polarization) and AOLP (azimuth of linear polarization) of the skylight.

Keywords: Remote Sensing; Polarization effects, Atmosphere, Skylight, Instruments.

INTRODUCTION

The atmosphere is an important environment element for human beings, and it is an indispensable natural resource. Earth's radiation balance is determined by the combination of aerosols, clouds, atmospheric gases, and surface reflections in the atmosphere. When the solar radiation passes through the atmosphere, it is scattered by the atmospheric particles, which will cause the polarization of light. In general, the primary scattering of atmospheric particles causes the sky polarization to produce a positive value, while the multiple scattering causes the sky polarization to produce a negative value.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In atmospheric polarization measurement, Stokes vector S is usually used to describe the polarization state of polarized beam. Stokes vector $S = [S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4]^T$ can be expressed as another form $S = [I, Q, U, V]^T$, where I is the total intensity of light, Q and U are linearly polarized light in two orthogonal directions, and V is circularly polarized light. In atmospheric polarization measurement, circular polarized light V is usually ignored because linear polarized light is the most common type of polarization in nature [2].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The sky was clear, and the air quality index is excellent. Because the lens was upward to the zenith, the top of the image corresponds to the

south direction of the geography, the bottom of the image corresponding to the north direction, the left corresponding to the west direction, and the right corresponding to the east direction, which is slightly different from the ordinary map. We transformed the RGB information of color image into gray information, and calculate Stokes component I, Q, U, DOLP and AOLP according to the formulas.

Fig.1. shows the change of sky polarization information in the whole day.

Figure 1. Daily variation of Stokes component of skylight

We can see the change rule of Stokes components I, Q and U. The light intensity I is largest at the solar spot, and sharply decreases towards the surrounding. Q component and U component are all zero at the position of the sun, which is an isolated point, and both components have the symmetrical axis with the minimum value. As shown in the blue strip in the figure, with the movement of the sun, the symmetrical axis rotates against the direction of the sun's motion, and the minimum value of the symmetrical axis of the two components is nearly perpendicular to each other, especially at 10:00-15:00, because Q and U are the line polarized light

in two orthogonal directions [4].

Rayleigh model can accurately represent the degree of polarization distribution in sunny days, which proves the accuracy of the sun position calculation method and the degree of polarization calculation method. It can be seen from the experimental results that the degree of linear polarization in the whole sky decreases with the increase of the solar altitude angle, and the position of the atmospheric neutral point is related to the position of the sun. The linear degree of polarization presents an obvious circular distribution, which is often called halo phenomenon.

From the image of polarization angle in a clear sky, it can be seen that the concentration point of polarization angle is the position of atmospheric polarization neutral point. The position and shape of the polarization angle distribution are different with different solar height angles. It can be found that with the change of the position of the sun, the convergence point of the polarization angle of the whole sky revolves around the zenith. When the solar altitude angle is high, we can only observe one convergence point of the sky polarization angle, and we can only see one convergence point for most of the day. Only when the solar altitude angle is low, such as the image at about 16:00 p.m., can we observe another convergence point.

CONSLUSION

In cloudy weather, the clouds cut off the complete polarization ring, however, the change trend of polarization can still be seen, and the neutral point area of the atmosphere in the sky is still obvious. In sunny days, the value of sky polarization is large, and the circular distribution is relatively complete; in cloudy conditions, the value of sky polarization is small, and the circular distribution is irregular.

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